

MULTI-SCALE SIMULATIONS OF FLUID/SOLID HYBRID COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

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1 Introduction

Hybrid fluid/solid materials are encountered in many technologies involving adhesives, coatings, lubricants, and composite materials. In such systems the interaction between the adsorbed molecules and the solid surfaces control the overall performance of the multiphase material system [1]. Here we present a hierarchical multi-scale approach in order to study complex multi-phase nanocomposite systems. Our approach combines quantum calculations and dynamic simulations from different levels of description. Our primary goal is to study the effect of confinement on the structural and dynamical properties of liquid systems, for a variety of materials.

2 Simulation Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of three stages described below. Different fluid/solid hybrid systems are modeled: (a) Benzene/gold, (b) Polyethylene/graphite and (c) Polystyrene/gold.

2.1 Ab-initio calculations

The first stage of our approach concern detailed ab-initio density functional theory (DFT) calculations of a single molecule adsorbed on a solid/metal surface. These calculations allow us to extract accurately the interaction energy between the molecule and the solid surface. Various molecule/metal systems have been modeled: Benzene/Au, Styrene/Au, Ethylene/Au. Density functional theory calculations were performed using the VASP code [2,3] We have also included dispersion interactions (via a self-consistent implementation of the van der Waals exchange-

correlation functional [2]) since they are crucial for the adsorption of molecules on the solid surface.

Figure 1 shows the adsorption sites on the Au(111) surface. The top site (T) is above a surface atom, the bridge site (B) is midway between adjacent top sites and the hcp and fcc hollow sites (H1 and H2) are situated in the midpoint of three top sites, as shown in Figure 1. Geometry relaxations were carried out at each high-symmetry site of the Au(111) surface. The difference in structure and energy between the two hollow sites is negligible.

The adsorption energy, E_{ads} , is defined as $E_{\text{ads}} = E_{\text{bnz}} + E_{\text{surf}} - E_{\text{tot}}$, where E_{tot} , E_{bnz} and E_{surf} are the energies of the whole system, the isolated benzene molecule and the isolated surface, respectively.

Fig.1. a) The Au(111) surface showing a benzene molecule on the fcc hollow site, H2, oriented with angle $\theta = 30$. Various adsorption sites are shown. The parallelogram indicates a surface unit cell. The vector v , which connects two opposite carbons along the plane of the benzene molecule, is used in the structural analysis. b) Benzene oriented vertically above a hollow site.

The adsorption energy is slightly larger for the hollow site than the bottom and top sites. However, the differences between the different sites are rather small, implying that the surface does not have strong

site dependence for the benzene molecule. On the top site the benzene prefers an orientation with the C–H bond parallel to the crystallographic a or b axis. The binding distance is 3.22 Å for the bridge and hollow sites whereas for the top site it is slightly larger (3.34 Å).

Often vdW forces are neglected, since they are considered weak in comparison to chemisorptions energies and DFT calculations without vdW forces show little or no bonding with gold. However, it is clear from the adsorption energies that there is a strong interaction between benzene and gold, which is almost entirely due to vdW forces. This is not surprising since both the benzene molecule and the gold have relatively high polarisabilities.

2.2 Development of a classical force field.

The second part of our hierarchical simulation approach, that combines methods from different levels of description, involves the development of an accurate classical atomistic force field for the molecule-surface interaction. [3]

Here for the classical simulations we use a model in which all surface (Au) atoms are presented explicitly. Then, we obtain proper pair potentials for the molecule/surface interaction (in our case Au-C and Au-H) using the detailed DFT calculations. Different functional forms can be used for the pair intermolecular potentials. A common choice is the typical Lennard-Jones (LJ) 12-6 potential:

$$V_{LJ}(r_{i,j}) = 4\epsilon_{i,j} \left[\left(\sigma_{i,j} / r_{i,j} \right)^{12} - \left(\sigma_{i,j} / r_{i,j} \right)^6 \right].$$

Alternatively, a more detailed pair potential such as the Morse potential can be used to describe the molecule-surface interaction:

$$V_{Morse}(r_{i,j}) = D_{i,j} \left[\exp(-2\alpha_{i,j}(r_{i,j} - r_{0i,j})) - 2\exp(-\alpha_{i,j}(r_{i,j} - r_{0i,j})) \right]$$

where the minimum of the potential has a depth of D at a distance $r = r_0$. The parameter α determines the shape/width of the potential. In both functional forms indices i and j denote the atom types, e.g. i is an Au atom and j is a C or H atom.

Our goal is to find the set of non-bonded parameters that best describe the DFT data, i.e. adsorption energies. This is not a trivial numerical problem, since it involves a fitting over a many-parameter space. To achieve this we use an optimization algorithm, which is based on Simulated Annealing (SA). The method is applied to molecules adsorbed on solid surfaces. The DFT data for the adsorption

energy as a function of the distance of the molecule from the surface are used as input. In the present case three adsorption sites (top, hollow and bridge) with two molecule orientations (flat and vertical) are considered. The whole optimization procedure involves the following stages:

1. The DFT data for the adsorption (non-bonded interaction) energy of the molecule near to the surface, $E_{\text{ads}}^{\text{DFT}}(z)$, are taken from detailed ab-initio calculations.

2. Initial values for non-bonded pair interaction parameters between molecule atoms and surface atoms are chosen. They can be: (a) LJ or (b) Morse potentials. Then the atomistic molecule-surface non-bonded interaction energy, $E_{\text{ads}}^{\text{A}}(z)$, for the specific set of force field parameters is calculated. Here we treat the benzene/Au and the styrene/Au systems in all atom description. We have two non-bonded pair interactions: C-Au and H-Au.

3. Through an optimization scheme, based on simulated annealing (SA), the parameters of the non-bonded interaction are chosen in order to minimize a target cost function. The cost function is defined as the difference between the quantum and classical molecule-surface interaction energies, for all distances and all different configurations (various adsorption sites and orientations) [3].

In the first two parameterisations examined here, LJ type non-bonded interaction potentials were chosen and the values of the LJ interaction potentials $\epsilon_{\text{Au-C}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{Au-C}}$ were obtained by minimizing a cost function for the hollow site, denoted "hffLJ", or the top site, denoted "tffLJ". The best set of data for the hffLJ and tffLJ parameterizations are shown in Figure 2(a,b). Note that it is not possible to find a set of LJ parameters to describe all DFT data (molecule-surface distances) for each adsorption site; thus the cost function were adjusted so that, the obtained force field reproduce better the DFT position and depth of the minimum. In both hffLJ and tffLJ cases the agreement between the DFT data and the atomistic force field is reasonably good at the minimum of the interaction as well as for longer distances. However, there are discrepancies in the short range repulsive regime where the LJ based atomistic potential is too steep in comparison with the DFT data as well as some small deviations at long distances. This is a clear indication that the typical LJ 12-6 pair potential is not the best choice

for describing the interaction between molecules and surfaces.

Fig.2. Comparison between the force field adsorption energy curves and DFT results using a LJ interaction fitted to (a) top, flat orientation (tffLJ) (b) hollow, flat orientation (hffLJ), and a Morse interaction for (c) top, flat and top, vertical orientations (tffM) and (d) hollow, flat and hollow, vertical orientations (hffM).

In the second set of parameterisations non-bonded Morse potentials were used and the values of $D_{i,j}$, $\alpha_{i,j}$, and $r_{0i,j}$ were obtained by minimizing the cost function for the hollow site, denoted "hffM" or the top site, denoted "tffM". In this parameterisation we optimised both the C-Au and the H-Au pair potentials. The best set of data for the hffM and tffM parameterizations are shown in Figure 2(c,d). As we can see the agreement between the classical and the ab-initio molecule-surface interaction energies is very good for the entire range of distances studied

here. This is a clear indication that a Morse-like interaction potential, which shape and width can be modified, is the proper choice to describe complicated many-body molecule-surface interactions in the classical level as pair atom ones. The transferability of the parameters for different orientations of benzene was checked by comparing the energy versus distance curves for a molecule (benzene, styrene, or ethylene) in different orientations. More details about the development of the classical force field, using detailed DFT data can be found elsewhere [3].

2.3 Atomistic MD Simulations

In the third stage atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of hybrid molecule/solid materials are performed [3,4]. Different systems have been studied: benzene/gold (Be/Au), polystyrene/gold (PS/Au) and polyethylene/graphite (PE/Gr). Atomistic MD simulations have been performed at constant temperature: (a) $T=300\text{K}$ for the Benzene/Au and (b) $T=450\text{K}$ for the PS/Au and PE/Gr systems. A time step of 1fs was used and all the simulations were run for 100-300ns, after equilibration. Various model systems were simulated for different range of confinement.

Fig.3. Snapshots of benzene films of different thicknesses: a,b) S1, c) S2, d) S3 and e) S4.

As an example in Figure 3 we present typical snapshots, taken from the MD simulations, for modeled Benzene/Au films (S1-S4 systems). The averaged film thicknesses of the model systems studied here, are approximately 1.17 nm, 1.18 nm, 2.09 nm, 4.18 nm and 8.36 nm for S1a, S1b, S2, S3 and S4, respectively. These thicknesses correspond to about 2.3, 2.3 4.2, 8.4 and 16.7 molecular diameters respectively. A clear layering is seen at

the interfaces for all systems. In the two thinner films, S1 and S2, the layers are visually distinct, with the S2 film having five distinct layers and the S1 film having two distinct layers. In addition the smallest film exhibits two different stable configurations, shown in Figure 3(a,b), and an additional ordering along the crystallographic directions. In contrast the two bigger systems S3 and S4 show a clear ordering only for the first layer whereas at longer distances from the surface a more bulk-like behavior is seen. Overall, the strength of the confinement varies from bulk-like to very confined, highly ordered systems.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Density - Structure

The time-averaged molecular (center-of-mass) density profiles, $\rho(z)$, as a function of the distance from the metal surfaces (z -direction) of the model films studied here, are shown in Fig. 4. For these larger systems we observe the typical oscillatory profile characteristic of fluid-solid interfacial systems. The density has clear peaks near to the solid surfaces with their height decreasing as the distance from the surface increases. The largest system (S4) also exhibits a clear bulk-like region in the centre of the film with the density equal to the bulk density ($\rho=0.85\text{g/cm}^3$ at $T=300\text{K}$, $P=1\text{atm}$). Overall, the effect of the interface on the density profiles extends $\sim 2.5\text{nm}$ from the gold surface.

Fig.4. Time averaged molecular density profiles for S3 and S4 (4.3 and 8.6-nm films) Benzene/Au systems and of the bulk benzene.

The orientational order of the confined Benzene molecules has been also studied. The main question here is related with molecular orientation tendencies induced by the confinement. The orientation of a molecule can be quantified by calculating the second rank order parameter. For an arbitrary vector, along the molecule, v , this is defined as $P_2(\cos(\theta)) = 3/2 \langle \cos^2(\theta) \rangle - 1/2$, where θ is the angle of the vector v with the z coordinate axis; i.e. in our case normal to the surface, and $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average of all molecules in the system. Here, in order to analyze the orientation of the entire benzene molecule, we choose as v the vector connecting the two opposite carbons along the plane of the molecule (see Figure 1a). The limiting $P_2(\cos(\theta))$ values of 0.5, 1.0 and 0.0 corresponds to the benzene oriented parallel to the surface, perpendicular to the surface and random orientation respectively.

In Figure 5 we show a typical profile for one of the systems studied here (Be/Au). It is clear a strong tendency of the molecules close to the surfaces, up to distances of about 2.0-nm, to orient parallel to the surface plane. Beyond this, in the middle of the film the orientation of the molecules becomes random. Similar is the case for all other systems.

Fig.5. Orientational order parameter $P_2(\cos(\theta))$ for systems S3 and S4,

3.2 Dynamics

Segmental dynamics of molecules is analyzed through time auto-correlation functions (ACFs) of a vector v connecting the two carbons along the plane of the molecule. Data for the autocorrelation

functions (ACFs) of the second Legendre polynomial, $P_2(t)$, as a function of distance from the surface planes are give information about the dependence of the orientation dynamics as a function of distance from the solid surfaces. In Figure 6 we present $P_2(t)$ of benzene molecules, belonging to different adsorption layers, defined by the minimums in the density profile. It is clear that the relaxation is slower in the first layer (atoms very close to the solid surface) whereas it is very close to the bulk behavior for all the molecules belonging in different layers. Through these curves relaxation times can be calculated which are very close to existing experimental data [3].

Fig.6. Time autocorrelation functions of $P_2(t)$, analyzed layer-by-layer, for a Be/Au 8.6~nm film.

It is quite common to fit the long time regime of such autocorrelation functions with modified stretched exponential Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts (KWW) functions of the form: $P_2(t) = A \exp(-(t/t_{KWW})^b)$. Here t_{KWW} is a characteristic relaxation time and b is the stretch exponent accounting from deviation from the Debye behavior. A is a pre-exponential factor that takes into account relaxation processes (like bond vibrations and angle librations) at very short time scales.

The curves of Figure 6 can be accurately fitted with KWW functions for time scales above about 0.5 ps. Especially for the first adsorbed layer only times up to about 100 ps can be fitted since for 20 longer times $P_2(t)$ reaches a constant value. We found that the relaxation time of the benzene molecules very

close to the gold surfaces (first adsorption layer) is more than five times slower than the bulk value. The relaxation time of the molecules belonging in the second and third adsorption layer is slightly larger (about 20% and 10% respectively) than the bulk one, whereas it attains the bulk value for distances after the second adsorbed layer.

The stretch exponent β of the bulk unconstrained fluid is about 0.9, showing small deviations from the ideal (simple exponential) behavior. The value of β is much smaller for the molecules belonging in the first adsorption layer ($\beta = 0.6$) showing a broader, compared to bulk, distribution of relaxation times close to the surface. Overall, the effect of the interface on the orientational dynamics of the bigger systems extends mainly to the molecules next to the surfaces (first adsorption layer); i.e. about 5 (Å) from the gold surface.

Fig.7. Translational center-of-mass xy mean square displacements of all confined benzene systems studied here.

In the last part of the results section we discuss the translational dynamics of the confined benzene molecules. This can be quantified through mean square displacement (MSDs) of the molecules center-of-mass in the xy plane (free directions) parallel to the gold surfaces: $DR_{xy}(t) = \langle (R_{xy}(t) - R_{xy}(0))^2 \rangle$, where $R(t)$ is the position of the center-of-mass at time t and the brackets denote the statistical average over all molecules present in the model systems. Results about DR_{xy} for the Be/Au systems studied here are shown Figure 7. The bulk, as well as the two bigger systems (S3 and S4) exhibit as expected non-linear anomalous dynamics

for short times (up to about 50 ps), and a linear Fickian dynamics at longer times. It is also clear that the xy translational mobility of the two bigger systems is slower, but within the same order of magnitude, than the bulk free dynamics. The behavior of the two smaller, more confined systems is very different. Both S1 and S2 films are practically frozen, i.e. there are only small vibrations of the benzene molecules, of about 0.4-0.6 Å. The long-time diffusion coefficient coefficient of adsorbed segments normal to the solid surface can be studied by mapping the MSDs of the MD trajectories onto the solution of a macroscopic diffusion equation. The whole procedure is described elsewhere [4]. Extracted self diffusion coefficients are reported as a function of film thickness in Figure 8, which shows the diffusion coefficient (scaled with the bulk diffusion coefficient) as a function of both time and distance from the solid surface. Obviously D depends strongly on the thickness d of the layer next to graphite they lie at the beginning of diffusion: the closer the layer to the graphite plane (i.e., the smaller the value of d), the slower the segmental mobility. It is seen that d must be at least 90 Å, i.e., 6-7 R_g , for the diffusion coefficient D in the C_{78} PE film to be equal to that in the bulk C_{78} melt. Experimental studies with other polymer melt/solid surface systems have proposed totally different values for such a distance, ranging from 3-4 R_g [3] to 25 R_g [4].

Figure 8: Diffusion coefficient, D , of adsorbed segments as a function of the thickness d of the

film from the graphite plane and how it changes with time.

Current work involves the extension of the proposed methodology to mesoscopic description using proper coarse-grained (CG) models. To achieve this, a methodology to develop CG models from the atomistic description, proper for bulk polymeric systems, will be extended to hybrid nanocomposite materials [5].

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